

Medicinal flowering plants distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia: The diversity and proposing some solutions for development

Ha Thu Bui ¹, Han Ngoc Le ² and Bach The Tran ^{2,3,*}

¹ Hanoi National University of Education, 136 Xuan Thuy, Cau Giay, Ha Noi, Vietnam.

² Institute of Ecology and Biological Resources, Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology, 18 Hoang Quoc Viet, Cau Giay, Ha Noi, Vietnam.

³ Graduate University of Science and Technology, Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology, 18 Hoang Quoc Viet, Cau Giay, Ha Noi, Vietnam.

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Abstract

The list of medicinal plants distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia has not been published systematically, leading to many difficulties in developing medicinal plants distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia. The most important goal is to build a list of medicinal flowering plants with information about specific medicinal uses. The paper assessed the diversity of species, genera, families and classes of the medicinal flowering plants (Magnoliophyta) distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia. The study has enumerated 922 species, 600 genera, 140 families, 2 classes of Magnoliophyta, distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia. Plants for timber with 61 species (1 class, 30 families, 55 genera). Ornamental plants with 93 species (2 classes, 32 families, 77 genera). Edible plants (edible fruits, seeds) with 86 species (2 classes, 38 families, 70 genera). Plants for essential oil with 11 species (2 classes, 7 families, 10 genera). Vegetables with 99 species (2 classes, 43 families, 80 genera). Dyed plants with 28 species (1 class, 13 families, 23 genera). Plants for fibre with 4 species (2 classes, 4 families, 4 genera). Plants for food of animal with 48 species (2 classes, 10 families, 32 genera). A model built for research and development of those species based on comprehensive cooperations and supports from agriculture, construction, fashion, forestry, food, ornamental and pharmaceutical organizations. The results provide a lot of valuable information, contributing to the development of cooperation of Vietnam and Indonesia on medicinal plant diversity research and application orientation.

Keywords: Magnoliophyta; Vietnam; Indonesia; Diversity; Development

1. Introduction

Scientific cooperations between Vietnam and Indonesia have been increasingly developed in recent years, including research on medicinal plant diversity. In order to facilitate the support of Vietnamese scientists to study plant diversity in Indonesia, as well as contribute to the development and application of useful plant species, while most plant taxonomists of Vietnam only know about Vietnamese plants, it is necessary to select a list of medicinal plant species that are distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia. For that reason, we have studied on the diversity of taxon ranks of medicinal plants of Magnoliophyta distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia.

Objectives: Compare medicinal taxa of Magnoliophyta (also known as flowering plants) which are distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia, contributing to the development of cooperation for the 2 countries on plant diversity research and application orientation.

* Corresponding author: Bach The Tran

2. Material and methods

2.1. The material studied

Specimens stored at the herbaria (HN herbarium of Institute of Ecology and Biological Resources (IEBR), Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology (VAST); VNM herbarium of Institute of Tropical Biology (ITB), VAST).

2.2. Research subjects

The medicinal plant taxa of the Magnoliophyta distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia.

2.3. Research content

Building a list of medicinal plant species belonging to the Magnoliophyta distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia; Evaluation of the diversity of taxon levels in the Magnoliophyta distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia (species, genera, families, classes).

2.4. Research methods

Establish list of species in both Vietnam and Indonesia based on references [1-52], investigations and study on specimens at the herbaria. Identify species based on the morphological comparison method. Scientific names of species and families according to the Checklist of plants in Vietnam (Nguyen TB, 2003, 2005) [1]. Names of 49 diseases according to Vo VC (2012) [26].

Coding uses/diseases: C: Ornamental plant; Ed: Edible (fruit, seed); Es: Essential oil; G: Timber; Nh: Dye; S: Fibre; R: Vegetable; T: Medicinal plant; ThA: Food for animal.

1: Tranquillizer; 2: Vaginitis; 3: Paralytic; 4: Obese; 5: Flu; 6: Eyesore; 7: Toothache; 8: Detoxify; 9: Syphilis; 10: Asthma; 12: Gonorrhoea; 13: Dysentery; 14: Galactopoietic; 15: Diuretic; 16: Mumps; 17: Snake bite; 18: Urolithiasis; 19: Malaria; 20: Rheumatism; 21: Diabetes; 22: Heart and blood pressure diseases; 23: Hemorrhoids; 24: Cancer; 25: Gastritis; 26: Hepatitis; 27: Keratitis; 28: Sore throat; 29: Encephalitis; 30: Nephritis; 31: Sinusitis; 32: Sterile; 33: Cirrhosis; 34: Brain hemorrhage; 35: Pimple; 36: Hemostatic; 37: Fracture; 38: Burned; 39: Pneumonia; 40: Bronchitis; 41: Hurt fall; 42: Irregular menstruation; 43: Kidney stone; 44: Measles; 45: Headache; 46: Inflammatory bowel; 47: Oedema; 48: Otitis; 49: Pertussis; 50: Scrofulous (Note: 11: a disease is not mentioned, therefore, there are 49 diseases / medical uses).

- Establishment of the list of medicinal flowering plants in both Vietnam and Indonesia.
- Coding families, order of families according to the Checklist of plants in Vietnam (Nguyen TB, 2003, 2005) (appendix 1) [1].
- Investigations in Vietnam from 2007 to 2021. Study on 11826 specimens of 3336 species collected from the investigations. Study on 19369 specimens of 5166 species stored at herbaria of Vietnam (HN, VNM).
- Application of Microsoft Access for data management and analysis.
- Based on the plant data of Magnoliophyta in Vietnam, statistic species distributed in Indonesia.
- Based on the plant data of Magnoliophyta in some neighboring countries, perform additional statistics of species also distributed in Vietnam and Indonesia.
- Compile a list of plant species belonging to Magnoliophyta distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia. Collect data on their use values. Build the list of medicinal flowering plants.
- Nomenclature correction according to Checklist of Plant Species of Vietnam, vol. 2, 3 (Nguyen TB (editor) et al., 2003, 2005) [1], <http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org> [50], www.tropicos.org [51].
- Evaluation of the diversity of plant taxon levels and the uses for Magnoliophyta (species, genera, families, classes).
- Proposing some solutions for development.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. List of flowering plants distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia (appendix 2)

Diversity of species, genera, families and classes of Magnoliophyta distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia.

The study has enumerated 922 species, 600 genera, 140 families, 2 classes of Magnoliophyta, distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia.

3.1.1. Diversity of classes (2 classes)

Magnoliopsida has 766 species, accounting for 83.1% of the total species. Liliopsida has 156 species, accounting for 16.9% of the total species.

3.1.2. Diversity of families (140 families)

The 10 species-rich families are FABACEAE (97 species, 10.5%), ASTERACEAE (87 species, 9.4%), EUPHORBIACEAE (49 species, 5.3%), CYPERACEAE (46 species, 5.0%), LAMIACEAE (32 species, 3.5%), RUBIACEAE (28 species, 3.0%), ORCHIDACEAE (27 species, 2.9%), MORACEAE (24 species, 2.6%), VERBENACEAE (23 species, 2.5%), CAESALPINIACEAE (23 species, 2.5%). A total of 10 families includes 436 species, 47.3%.

3.1.3. Diversity of genera (600 genera)

The 10 genera with the highest number of species are *Cyperus* (20 species, 2.2%), *Ficus* (15 species, 1.6%), *Crotalaria* (13 species, 1.4%), *Indigofera* (9 species, 1.0%), *Blumea* (7 species, 0.8%), *Fimbristylis* (7 species, 0.8%), *Ardisia* (6 species, 0.7%), *Mallotus* (6 species, 0.7%), *Syzygium* (6 species, 0.7%), *Trichosanthes* (6 species, 0.7%). A total of 10 genera including 95 species, accounting for 10.3%.

Diverse in use value

- Plants for timber: 61 species (1 class, 30 families, 55 genera).
- 10 families with the highest number of species: EUPHORBIACEAE 13 species, MIMOSACEAE 5 species,
- APOCYNACEAE 4 species, CAESALPINIACEAE 4 species, FABACEAE 3 species, LAURACEAE 3 species, MORACEAE 3 species, ANACARDIACEAE 2 species, MYRTACEAE 2 species, SYMPLOCACEAE 2 species, Each of the other families has 1 species.
- 5 genera with the highest number of species: *Alstonia* 3 species, *Adenanthera* 2 species, *Albizia* 2 species, *Cinnamomum* 2 species, *Symplocos* 2 species. Each of the other genera has 1 species.
 - Ornamental plants: 93 species (2 classes, 32 families, 77 genera).
- 10 families with the highest number of species: ORCHIDACEAE 16 species, ASTERACEAE 14 species, FABACEAE 7 species, MORACEAE 7 species, CAESALPINIACEAE 5 species, LILIACEAE 4 species, ACANTHACEAE 3 species, ARECACEAE 3 species, RUBIACEAE 3 species, ZINGIBERACEAE 3 species. Each of the other families has less than 3 species.
- 9 genera with the highest number of species: *Ficus* 6 species, *Cymbidium* 3 species, *Erythrina* 3 species, *Ixora* 3 species, *Cassia* 2 species, *Chrysanthemum* 2 species, *Coreopsis* 2 species, *Cyperus* 2 species, *Magnolia* 2 species. Each of the remaining genera has 1 species.
 - Edible plants (edible fruits, seeds): 86 species (2 classes, 38 families, 70 genera).
- 10 families with the highest number of species: MORACEAE 10 species, RUTACEAE 8 species, EUPHORBIACEAE 7 species, SAPINDACEAE 6 species, ANACARDIACEAE 5 species, ROSACEAE 5 species, MYRTACEAE 4 species, LAMIACEAE 3 species, RUBIACEAE 3 species, VERBENACEAE 3 species. Each of the other families has less than 3 species.
- 11 genera with the highest number of species: *Rubus* 4 species, *Syzygium* 4 species, *Artocarpus* 3 species, *Alpinia* 2 species, *Antidesma* 2 species, *Citrus* 2 species, *Clausena* 2 species, *Ficus* 2 species, *Glycosmis* 2 species, *Mangifera* 2 species, *Sonneratia* 2 species. Each of the remaining genera has 1 species.
 - Plants for essential oil: 11 species (2 classes, 7 families, 10 genera).
- ASTERACEAE 3 species, LAMIACEAE 2 species, MYRTACEAE 2 species. Each of the 4 families has 1 species: CYPERACEAE, LAURACEAE, MAGNOLIACEAE, ZINGIBERACEAE.
- genera, of which *Ocimum* has 2 species, Each of the remaining 9 genera has 1 species.
 - Vegetables: 99 species (2 classes, 43 families, 80 genera).
- ASTERACEAE 28 species, EUPHORBIACEAE 6 species, ARACEAE 5 species, LAMIACEAE 5 species, APOCYNACEAE 4 species, CUCURBITACEAE 4 species, FABACEAE 3 species, SCROPHULARIACEAE 3 species, APIACEAE 2 species, BEGONIACEAE 2 species, CAESALPINIACEAE 2 species, MORACEAE 2 species, MYRSINACEAE 2 species, VIOLACEAE 2 species. Each of the remaining families has 1 species.
- Genera with the highest number of species: *Blumea* 3 species, *Limnophila* 3 species, *Rauvolfia* 3 species; *Acmella* 2 species, *Ardisia* 2 species, *Artemisia* 2 species, *Begonia* 2 species, *Claoxylon* 2 species, *Clinopodium* 2 species, *Emilia* 2 species, *Ficus* 2 species, *Sesbania* 2 species, *Sonchus* 2 species, *Trichosanthes* 2 species, *Viola* 2 species, *Zehneria* 2 species. Each of the remaining genera has 1 species.
 - Dyed plants: 28 species (1 class, 13 families, 23 genera).

- CAESALPINIACEAE 4 species, FABACEAE 4 species, MIMOSACEAE 4 species, COMBRETACEAE 3 species ALANGIACEAE 2 species, EUPHORBIACEAE 2 species, RHIZOPHORACEAE 2 species, VERBENACEAE 2 species. Each of the other families has 1 species.
- *Alangium* 2 species, *Albizia* 2 species, *Avicennia* 2 species, *Butea* 2 species, *Terminalia* 2 species. Each of the remaining genera has 1 species.
 - Plants for fibre: 4 species (2 classes, 4 families, 4 genera).
- Each of the 4 families has 1 species: ARECACEAE, ASCLEPIADACEAE, EUPHORBIACEAE, STERCULIACEAE.
- Each of the 4 genera with 1 species: *Caryota*, *Gongronemopsis*, *Macaranga*, *Pentapetes*.
 - Plants for food of animal: 48 species (2 classes, 10 families, 32 genera).
- FABACEAE 20 species, CYPERACEAE 14 species, POACEAE 6 species, ASTERACEAE 2 species. Each of the other families has 1 species: ARACEAE, CAESALPINIACEAE, COMMELINACEAE, MORACEAE, RUTACEAE, STERCULIACEAE.
- Genera: *Cyperus* has 9 species, 2 genera have 3 species *Indigofera*, *Sesbania*. 4 genera have 2 species *Fimbristylis*, *Grona*, *Setaria*, *Vigna*. Each of the other genera has 1 species.

3.2. Proposing some solutions for development (figure 1)

Although the proposals are theoretically, but if the cooperations and comprehensive support from many agencies are achieved, the development of the medicinal plants will bring positive results. To achieve this, there must be a group of expertise, the above data and linking companies.

Figure 1 Comprehensive and reasonable combined model for developing 922 medicinal plant species in both Vietnam and Indonesia

Appendixes

Appendix 1. Coding families, order of families according to the Checklist of plants in Vietnam (Nguyen TB, 2003, 2005) [1]. Families coded from 1 to 219 belong to Magnoliopsida, families coded from 220 to 265 belong to Liliopsida.

1: MAGNOLIACEAE. 2: ANNONACEAE. 5: HERNANDIACEAE. 6: CHLORANTHACEAE. 8: LAURACEAE. 9: SAURURACEAE. 10: PIPERACEAE. 11: ARISTOLOCHIACEAE. 14: NYMPHAEACEAE. 16: CERATOPHYLLACEAE. 17: ILLICIACEAE. 19: NELUMBONACEAE. 21: SARGENTODOXACEAE. 22: MENISPERMACEAE. 23: RANUNCULACEAE. 24: BERBERIDACEAE. 25: PAPAVERACEAE. 26: FUMARIACEAE. 28: ALTINGIACEAE. 29: PLATANACEAE. 31: ULMACEAE. 32: MORACEAE. 33: CANNABACEAE. 34: URTICACEAE. 35: CASUARINACEAE. 36: FAGACEAE. 37: BETULACEAE. 40: JUGLANDACEAE. 42: NYCTAGINACEAE. 43: MOLLUGINACEAE. 47: PORTULACEAE. 48: BASELLACEAE. 49: CARYOPHYLLACEAE. 50: AMARANTHACEAE. 51: CHENOPODIACEAE. 52: POLYGONACEAE. 54: DILLENACEAE. 57: DIPTEROCARPACEAE. 59: THEACEAE. 62: CLUSIACEAE. 63: HYPERICACEAE. 64: ELATINACEAE. 65: FLACOURTIACEAE. 67: VIOLACEAE. 70: PASSIFLORACEAE. 72: CARICACEAE. 73: CUCURBITACEAE. 75: BEGONIACEAE. 76: CAPPARACEAE. 78: BRASSICACEAE. 80: SALICACEAE. 87: STYRACACEAE. 88: SYMPLOCACEAE. 89: EBENACEAE. 90: SAPOTACEAE. 91: MYRSINACEAE. 92: PRIMULACEAE. 94: TILIACEAE. 95: STERCULIACEAE. 96: BOMBACACEAE. 97: MALVACEAE. 100: EUPHORBIACEAE. 102: THYMELEACEAE. 105: ITEACEAE. 106: HYDRANGEACEAE. 109: CRASSULACEAE. 111: ROSACEAE. 113: MIMOSACEAE. 114: CAESALPINIACEAE. 115: FABACEAE. 116: CONNARACEAE. 120: LYTHRACEAE. 123: RHIZOPHORACEAE. 125: COMBRETACEAE. 126: MYRTACEAE. 127: MELASTOMATACEAE. 128: ONAGRACEAE. 131: HALORAGACEAE. 132: ANACARDIACEAE. 133: SIMAROUBACEAE. 134: RUTACEAE. 135: MELIACEAE. 136: STAPHYLEACEAE. 138: SAPINDACEAE. 139: HIPPOCASTANACEAE. 141: SABIACEAE. 143: LINACEAE. 148:

OXALIDACEAE. 151: BALSAMINACEAE. 152: POLYGALACEAE. 156: AUCUBACEAE. 157: ALANGIACEAE. 161:

ARALIACEAE. 162: APIACEAE. 163: AQUIFOLIACEAE. 164: ICACINACEAE. 166: CELASTRACEAE. 168: RHAMNACEAE.

169: VITACEAE. 170: LEEACEAE. 171: OLEACEAE. 174: OPILIACEAE. 175: ERYTHROPALACEAE. 176: CARDIOPTERIDACEAE. 179: LORANTHACEAE. 182: ELAEAGNACEAE. 183: PROTEACEAE. 184: CAPRIFOLIACEAE. 185: VALERIANACEAE. 187: LOGANIACEAE. 189: APOCYNACEAE. 190: ASCLEPIADACEAE. 191: GENTINIACEAE. 192:

MENYANTHACEAE. 193: RUBIACEAE. 195: CONVOLVULACEAE. 196: CUSCUTACEAE. 197: HYDROPHYLLACEAE. 198: BORAGINACEAE. 199: SOLANACEAE. 200: BUDDLEJACEAE. 201: SCROPHULARIACEAE. 202: BIGNONIACEAE. 203: PEDALIACEAE. 205: GESNERIACEAE. 207: LENTIBULARIACEAE. 209: ACANTHACEAE. 211: VERBENACEAE. 212: LAMIACEAE. 213: CALLITRICHACEAE. 214: CAMPANULACEAE. 219: ASTERACEAE. 221: ALISMATACEAE. 229: CONVALLARIACEAE. 229: LILIACEAE. 230: HYPOXIDACEAE. 232: SMILACACEAE. 233: STEMONACEAE. 234:

DIOSCOREACEAE. 235: TACCACEAE. 238: IRIDACEAE. 244: COSTACEAE. 245: ZINGIBERACEAE. 246: CANNACEAE. 247: MARANTACEAE. 248: ORCHIDACEAE. 249: JUNCACEAE. 250: CYPERACEAE. 251: BROMLELIACEAE. 252: COMMELINACEAE. 259: POACEAE. 260: ARECACEAE. 261: ARACEAE. 262: LEMNACEAE. 265: TYPHACEAE.

Appendix 2. Data of flowering plants in both Vietnam and Indonesia for each species are "Coded family-Scientific name-Coded Use (present or absent)-Coded Medical value (present or absent) /"

115-Abrus melanospermus subsp. melanospermus-T 15 20 26 / 115-Abrus precatorius-T 35 / 100-Acalypha hispida-T C / 100-Acalypha siamensis-T 15 / 209-Acanthus ebracteatus-T / 50-Achyranthes bidentata-T 20 22 28 / 219-Acmella calva-T 7 / 219-Acmella oleracea -T R 7 45 / 219-Acmella paniculata -T 7 20 / 219-Acmella uliginosa-T R 15 / 261-Acorus calamus-T C / 134-Acronychia pedunculata-T 35 41 / 100-Acethephila excelsa-T / 250-Actinoscirpus grossus-T / 113-Adenanthera microsperma-G T C Nh 13 / 113-Adenanthera pavonina-G T 20 / 70-Adenia heterophylla-T R 8 20 / 201-Adenosma glutinosa-T 3 17 20 26 / 201-Adenosma indiana-T 46 / 219-Adenostemma lavenia-T R 17 / 219-Adenostemma macrophyllum-T 7 20 / 206-Aeginetia acaulis-T 21 35 / 134-Aegle marmelos-T Ed R / 115-Aeschynomene aspera-T 17 / 115-Aeschynomene indica-T / 115-Aganope thyrsoiflora-T / 229-Agave vivipara-T / 116-Agelaea macrophylla-T 20 / 219-Ageratum conyzoides-T ThA 31 / 219-Ageratum houstonianum-T 31 / 133-Ailanthus triphysa-G T 2 13 / 157-Alangium chinense-T Nh 17 20 22 41 45 / 157-Alangium kurzii-G T 20 41 / 157-Alangium salviifolium-T Nh 9 10 15 / 113-Albizia chinensis-G T Nh 17 / 113-Albizia corniculata-T C 17 / 113-Albizia lebbekoides-G T Nh 17 / 100-Alchornea rugosa-T / 229-Allium ramosum-T R 2 / 261-Alocasia longiloba-T R / 245-Alpinia conchigera-T 20 45 / 245-Alpinia galanga-T Ed 7 8 13 / 245-Alpinia malaccensis-T C Ed / 245-Alpinia mutica-T / 189-Alstonia macrophylla-G T / 189-Alstonia rostrata -G T / 189-Alstonia spatulata -G T / 252-Amisotolype hispida-T / 261-Amorphophallus paeoniifolius-T / 169-Ampelocissus arachnoidea-T Ed / 169-Ampelocissus polythyrso-T 20 / 189-Amphineurion marginatum-T / 261-Anadendrum montanum-T R 17 19 / 58-Ancistrocladus tectorius-T / 209-Andrographis paniculata-T 8 11 13 28 35 / 248-Anoectochilus setaceus-T C 20 25 41 / 32-Antiaris toxicaria-T Ed 13 / 100-Antidesma acidum-T / 100-Antidesma bunius-T Ed / 100-Antidesma ghaesembilla-T Ed R / 100-Antidesma montanum-T / 135-Aphanamixis polystachya-T 17 / 115-Aphyllodium biarticulatum-T / 259-Apluda mutica-T ThA 17 / 100-Aporosa octandra var. octandra-G T Ed / 161-Aralia dasyphylla-T 20 41 / 161-Aralidium pinnatifidum-T / 22-

Arcangelisia flava-T 13 19 46 / 219-Arctium lappa-T R / 91-Ardisia colorata-T 12 / 91-Ardisia crispa-T R 7 13 35 / 91-Ardisia humilis-T Ed R / 91-Ardisia polysticta subsp. polysticta-T 37 41 46 / 91-Ardisia quinquegona-T 7 / 91-Ardisia villosa-T 41 / 260-Areca triandra-T C / 260-Arenga pinnata-T C 15 / 2-Artabotrys hexapetalus-T / 201-Artanema longifolium-T 6 9 18 20 / 219-Artemisia caruifolia var. caruifolia-T R / 219-Artemisia vulgaris-T Es R 20 / 32-Artocarpus altilis -T 13 17 47 / 32-Artocarpus integer-T Ed 1 14 22 / 32-Artocarpus lamellosus-T Ed / 32-Artocarpus rigidus-G T Ed 17 / 248-Arundina graminifolia-T C 17 20 26 47 / 190-Asclepias curassavica-T C / 231-Asparagus filicinus-T C / 219-Aster indicus-T C R 26 41 / 110-Astilbe rivularis-T C / 209-Asystasia gangetica-T C 8 / 211-Avicennia marina-T Ed Nh 13 / 211-Avicennia officinalis-T Nh / 219-Ayapana triplinervis -T 17 35 / 135-Azadirachta indica-T 17 19 20 / 165-Azima sarmentosa-T Ed 20 35 / 219-Baccharoides anthelmintica -T / 100-Balakata baccata -G T / 181-Balanophora fungosa subsp. indica-T / 181-Balanophora latisejala-T / 100-Baliospermum solanifolium -T / 130-Barringtonia acutangula-T R 17 / 130-Barringtonia asiatica-G / 130-Barringtonia racemosa-T 10 17 44 / 212-Basilicum polystachyon-T 2 20 / 114-Bauhinia hirsuta-T 17 / 114-Bauhinia viridescens-T / 75-Begonia aptera-T R 13 35 38 41 49 / 75-Begonia tenuifolia-T R 35 / 134-Bergera koenigii-T / 114-Biancaea decapetala-T 13 19 44 / 114-Biancaea sappan-G T Nh 13 / 219-Bidens biternata-T 17 46 / 219-Bidens pilosa-T R 23 / 148-Biophytum sensitivum-T 12 15 21 35 43 46 / 100-Bischofia javanica-G T Ed R / 219-Blumea balsamifera-T Es 5 / 219-Blumea densiflora-T / 219-Blumea fistulosa-T R / 219-Blumea hieraciifolia-T / 219-Blumea lacera-T R 8 35 / 219-Blumea lanceolaria-T R 15 / 219-Blumea sinuata-T 5 8 20 35 / 245-Boesenbergia rotunda-T 2 13 15 / 96-Bombax ceiba-T R 13 14 21 / 198-Bothriospermum zeylanicum-T C Ed 8 9 12 15 / 132-Bouea oppositifolia-G T Ed 38 / 115-Bowringia callicarpa-T 20 / 161-Brassaiopsis glomerulata-T 20 41 49 / 100-Breynia androgyna-T R / 100-Breynia temii-T C / 100-Bridelia ovata-G T / 100-Bridelia stipularis-T / 32-Broussonetia papyrifera-T Ed / 200-Buddleja asiatica-T 6 20 35 37 44 / 248-Bulbophyllum concinnum-T 25 40 / 250-Bulbostylis barbata-T / 250-Bulbostylis densa-T / 239-Burmannia coelestis-T / 115-Butea monosperma-T Nh 17 / 115-Butea superba-T Nh / 115-Cajanus scarabaeoides-T 20 / 115-Cajanus volubilis-T / 261-Caladium bicolor-T C 13 17 45 / 260-Calamus viminalis-T Ed / 248-Calanthe vestita-T C / 219-Calendula officinalis-T C 1 38 / 211-Callicarpa erioclona-T 12 / 211-Callicarpa longifolia-T 9 / 211-Callicarpa macrophylla-T 20 41 / 211-Callicarpa rubella-T Ed 2 8 20 / 62-Calophyllum inophyllum-T 20 26 35 38 41 42 50 / 190-Calotropis gigantea-T / 100-Calypha spiciflora-G T Ed / 2-Cananga odorata-T / 132-Canarium littorale-T / 115-Canavalia cathartica-T / 115-Canavalia rosea-T ThA / 193-Canthium horridum-T Ed / 76-Capparis micracantha-T Ed 10 15 22 40 / 123-Carallia brachiata-G T Ed 19 / 176-Cardiopteris quinqueloba-T R 7 17 / 250-Carex baccans-T / 250-Carex cruciata-T / 250-Carex filicina-T / 250-Carex phacota-T / 189-Carissa carandas-T / 219-Carpesium abrotanoides-T 28 40 / 219-Carpesium cernuum-T / 219-Carthamus tinctorius-T / 260-Caryota urens-T S 2 13 / 65-Casearia grewiifolia-T 15 / 114-Cassia fistula-T C Nh 17 / 114-Cassia grandis-T C Ed 13 17 19 44 / 193-Catunaregam tomentosa-T 17 / 169-Cayratia japonica-T 2 8 15 17 26 50 / 169-Cayratia mollissima-T / 169-Cayratia trifolia-T 2 35 / 166-Celastrus hindsii-T 12 26 42 / 166-Celastrus paniculatus-T / 31-Celtis timorensis-G T 23 41 / 219-Centipeda minima-T 1 6 13 17 19 31 40 49 / 189-Cerbera manghas-T / 189-Cerbera odollam-T / 123-Ceriops tagal-T Nh 19 / 114-Chamaecrista absus-T 6 23 / 114-Chamaecrista mimosoides-T ThA 17 30 47 / 114-Chamaecrista pumila-T / 193-Chassalia curviflora-T Ed 17 19 45 / 6-Chloranthus erectus-T 18 20 41 / 229-Chlorophytum laxum-T / 115-Christia obcordata-T / 115-Christia vespertilionis-T C 17 19 / 219-Chrysanthemum indicum-T C 13 17 22 26 29 35 45 / 219-Chrysanthemum vestitum-T C / 219-Cichorium intybus-T R 15 / 8-Cinnamomum burmanni-T 5 20 35 / 8-Cinnamomum iners-G T / 8-Cinnamomum subavenium -G T 20 41 / 135-Cipadessa baccifera-T 20 / 169-Cissus adnata-T / 169-Cissus discolor -T R / 169-Cissus quadrangularis-T 10 / 134-Citrus × aurantiifolia -T 5 49 / 134-Citrus × aurantium f. aurantium-T Ed / 134-Citrus × limon -T / 134-Citrus medica-T 18 / 134-Citrus reticulata-T Ed 8 / 100-Claoxylon indicum-T R 17 / 100-Claoxylon longifolium-T R / 134-Clausena anisata-T Ed 20 / 134-Clausena harmandiana-T ThA 40 45 / 134-Clausena lansium-T Ed 29 / 100-Cleistanthus monoicus-G T / 23-Clematis brevicaudata-T / 23-Clematis leschenaultiana-T / 76-Cleome chelidonii-T 5 10 17 26 / 211-Clerodendrum chinense-T C 2 17 20 22 35 42 / 211-Clerodendrum laevifolium-T / 211-Clerodendrum paniculatum-T 2 12 20 42 / 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4. Conclusion

The paper assessed the diversity of medicinal species, genera, families and classes of the Magnoliophyta distributed in both Vietnam and Indonesia. Establishment of comprehensive and reasonable combined model for developing 922 medicinal plant species in both Vietnam and Indonesia. The results provide a lot of valuable information, contributing to the development of cooperation of Vietnam and Indonesia on plant diversity research and orientation for application of medicinal plants.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors have no conflict of interests to declare.

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